

PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 3 LEARNERS IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN: BASIS FOR RESOURCE MATERIALS

Ivy V. Carlos

*Institute of Graduate and Professional Studies
Lyceum-Northwestern University, Dagupan City, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13868417>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of Grade 3 learners in Bacsay Elementary School, Camiling West District, Tarlac Province during the school year 2023-2024 through the quantitative-descriptive research design. The quantitative-descriptive research design was utilized to assess the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners based on the results of teacher-made tests during the school year 2023-2024 as well as their weaknesses in Araling Panlipunan. The acceptability of the developed resource materials was likewise determined based on evaluation of experts. Based on the findings, resource materials in the teaching of Araling Panlipunan were developed to address the weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan. The sources of data in this study were the teachers in Bacsay Elementary School who provided data to answer the sub-problems raised in the study with 21 Grade 3 learners as subjects of the study. Weighted mean was utilized to treat the data statistically. Summary of Findings: 1.0 Level of Performance in Araling Panlipunan of Grade 3 Learners There were no learners who obtained “outstanding” performance or rating of 95-100%. There were four Grade 3 learners or 19.05% who obtained 90-94% rating described as “above average” performance. There were five learners or 23.81% with 85-89% rating described as “average” performance. There were eight or 38.09% with 80-84% rating described as “fair” performance. Four learners or 19.05% obtained ratings of 75-79% described as “poor” performance. 2.0 Weaknesses of the Grade 3 Learners in Araling Panlipunan The Grade 3 learners are weak in the following skills/competencies: Natatalakay ang pamahalaan at ang mga mamamayan nito (71.68%) Natutukoy ang mga pagbabagong nangyayari sa lalawigan at sa kinabibilangang rehiyon (70.36%); Naipaliliwanag ang impluwensiya ng klima at lokasyon sa pagbuo at paghubog ng

pamumuhay sa isang lugar (67.71%); Naipaliliwanag ang kahalagahan ng pamahalaan (64.19%); Nailalarawan ang kultrang material ng unang Pilipino (62.41%); Pagpapahalaga sa mga bayani ng lalawigan at rehiyon (58.18%); Nasusuri ang mga uri ng likas na yaman (56.27%); Maagap at wastong pagtugon sa mga panganib na madalas maranasan ng sariling rehiyon (56.02%); Natutukoy ang relatibong lokasyon ng mga lalawigan sa rehiyon (54.18%); and Natatalakay ang kultura sa kinabibilangang rehiyon (51.80%).

3.0 Proposed Resource Materials Resource materials in Araling Panlipunan for Grade 3 learners were developed to address the identified weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners.

4.0 Acceptability of the Resource Materials In terms of content, all of the five criteria had WM that ranged from 3.50 to 4.17 for descriptive equivalent of “very acceptable.” The average WM is 3.73 described as “very acceptable.” In terms of quality of presentation, all of the three criteria had WM that ranged from 3.50 to 4.00 for descriptive equivalent of “very acceptable.” The average WM is 3.72 described as “very acceptable. In terms of physical make-up, all of the three criteria had WM that ranged from 3.67 to 4.33 for descriptive equivalent of “very acceptable”. The average WM is 4.00 described as “very acceptable.” The overall average weighted mean is 3.82 for descriptive equivalent of “very acceptable”. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: 1. Most of the Grade 3 learners are approaching proficiency which means most of the learning targets are fully or consistently met. This indicates they have a good grasp of concepts and skills in Araling Panlipunan. 2. Weaknesses in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners include the following: Natatalakay ang pamahalaan at ang mga mamamayan nito; natutukoy ang mga pagbabagong nagyayari sa lalawigan at sa kinabibilangang rehiyon; and naipaliliwanag ang impluwensiya ng klima at lokasyon sa pagbuo at paghubog ng pamumuhay sa isang lugar. 3. The proposed resource materials were developed to address the weaknesses in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners and improve their level of performance. 4. The proposed resource materials are very acceptable based on the evaluation of experts. Based on the conclusions drawn as a result of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered: 1. The developed resource materials should be considered for use by concerned authorities. 2. Parents and teachers should communicate regularly relative to the learners’ performance in school. 3. The developed resource materials should be tried out on a wider scale for further improvement. 4. Teachers should be encouraged to develop instructional materials particularly on subjects or topics where most learners encounter difficulties. 5. The school administration should provide support in the production of materials developed by teachers. 6. Other researchers may conduct similar studies on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

Keywords: *acceptability, level of performance, resource materials, weaknesses*

INTRODUCTION

Quality education in all levels is vital in preparing students for today’s modern and competitive world. The philosophy of education which should be the ultimate basis of any reform has to be relevant and responsive to the rapidly changing world.

In the pursuit of quality education, teachers as catalysts of change need to understand the techniques for effective teaching and classroom management, particularly in interacting with pupils. The teacher's role is crucial in the knowing learning-teaching process. Time and again the success of educational reforms has been found to be decisively dependent on the will to change as much as the quality of the teachers. No education system can rise too far beyond the level of the teachers in it (Pangilinan, 2021).

Educational initiative which has its roots in the commitment of the teaching force has not only prospect of success but also of constancy. Such change, like any human-based change, may appear to be slow, has its rate of obsolescence is also very low, compared to machine-based changes. The successful technologies have been precisely those which have used the skills and styles of the best teachers. Teachers are perhaps the most influential variable to develop a quality learning environment in the classroom. They are one of the most important factors in helping children learn.

In the learner-centered knowing-learning process, the teacher is not only a transmitter of discrete segments of knowledge. The teacher helps constantly to connect to the larger framework. He or she is also the learners' guide, counselor, and role model. Thus, the teacher is not a narrow specialist but a knowledge worker, a lifelong learner. In the perfection of the teaching process, the teacher and the learners are partners.

In addition to being a right, basic elementary education underpins the success of a society. Every year of elementary education increases a person's productivity and reduces their dependence on social resources. The goal of education is to enable children to learn, realize their full potential, and participate meaningfully in society. In spite of increasing enrolment rates, too many children are learning far less than what they are taught about or what they ought to learn in school. This low learning achievement is most frequently due to a combination of factors that include inadequate learning environments, inappropriate teaching methods and frequently unmotivated teachers, and the malnourishment and ill-health of children themselves. Enhancing the quality in education, therefore, must be based on developing educational systems that are integrated and responsive to the multiple obstacles to children's learning (Inocian, 2014).

A teacher is expected to acquire sufficient knowledge to be ahead of their pupils as well as skills in imparting that knowledge. Because of the increasing complexity of modern life, the teacher must have an appreciation of the social meaning and purpose of education as well as knowledge of the particular subject area, which needs to be taught in the light of its use in the development of the pupils and their future.

Crisolo (2017) stated that the social studies in the early childhood/elementary years are crucial if we expect the young people of this nation to become active, responsible citizens for maintaining the democratic values upon which this nation was established. Unless children acquire the foundations of knowledge, attitudes, and skills in social studies in the important elementary years, it is unlikely that teachers in the junior and senior high schools will be successful in preparing effective citizens for the 21st century.

The social studies are the study of political, economic, cultural, and environmental aspects of societies in the past, present, and future. For elementary school children, as well as for all age groups social studies have several purposes. The social studies equip them with the knowledge and understanding of the past necessary for coping with the present and planning for the future, enable them to understand and participate effectively in their world, and explain their relationship to other people and to social, economic, and political institutions. Social studies can provide students with the skills for productive problem solving and decision making, as well as for assessing issues and making thoughtful value judgments. Above all, the social studies help students to integrate these skills and understandings into a framework for responsible citizen participation, whether in their play group, the school, the community, or the world (Baliling, 2020).

The energy, curiosity, and imagination of young children lead them to action and interaction within their environment from a narrow, unilateral perspective. They live in a family, play in a peer group, and make decisions about how they will relate to other people, what to do in their free time, with whom to play, what books to read, and how to spend money. The larger social world penetrates their lives through television and other media, travel, family, and friends; but young children lack the conceptual base to integrate the new knowledge these experiences bring. They also lack the skills to account for other perspectives in solving problems or to anticipate long-range consequences when making decisions.

A planned K-12 social studies program directs and focuses these natural characteristics to help children understand and function in their personal and social worlds. These learnings must be developed systematically from an early age, so that children move from egocentric, random observations and experiences to a broader and more structured conceptual organization. Many times, teachers suggest that at the primary level everything they do is related to social studies, but it is important to recognize that an effective social studies program cannot be just a haphazard collection of unrelated activities. It must be organized systematically around concepts from history and the social sciences (Guimba, et.al., 2016).

Active, curious children need, want, and are able to learn skills that are taught and reinforced in social studies classes. These skills are required for processing information so that they can make generalizations and integrate new information into a developing system of knowledge.

Children formulate many of their attitudes and values toward society in the early years. The development of these attitudes and values occurs primarily outside the school setting. However, the social studies program should provide a setting for children to acquire knowledge of history and the social sciences and to be exposed to a broad variety of opinions, facilitating the formulation, reassessment, and affirmation of their beliefs.

The social studies program enables children to participate effectively now in the groups to which they belong and not to look only to their future participation as adults. The school itself serves as a laboratory for students to learn social participation directly

and not symbolically. Democratic and participatory school and classroom environments are essential to this type of real-world learning.

If the social studies are not part of the elementary curriculum, we cannot expect our children to be prepared to understand or participate effectively in an increasingly complex world. They need to encounter and reencounter, in a variety of contexts, the knowledge, concepts, skills, and attitudes that form the foundation for participation in a democratic society. Otherwise, we are in danger of disrupting the critical balance between individual and community needs. Social studies are intended to help children understand, evaluate, and make decisions regarding these often competing claims. The problem lies in developing a learning environment and pedagogy that are intellectually and developmentally appropriate.

It is understood that teaching social studies in the elementary schools is an essential part of the framework of an overall K-12 social studies program. The elementary school years are important in that they are the ones in which children develop a foundation for the entire social studies program and a beginning sense of efficacy as participating citizens of their world.

As pointed out by Macarandan (2014), basic skills of reading, writing, and computing are necessary but not sufficient to participate or even survive in a world demanding independent and cooperative problem solving to address complex social, economic, ethical, and personal concerns. Knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for informed and thoughtful participation in society require a systematically developed program focusing on concepts from history and the social sciences.

The decline in the quality of Philippine education especially at the elementary level prompted the Congressional Commission on Education to effect a reorganization in the elementary and secondary schools. The findings of the Commission showed that the average sixth grade pupil has mastered about half of the content of the basic subjects namely Mathematics, Science, English, Filipino and HEKASI/Araling Panlipunan.

It has been the goal of educators to raise the low quality of Philippine education. But in spite of huge investments in buildings, equipment and teaching aids, the rapid increase of pupils in the country tends to perpetuate low standards. The innovations and strategic actions launched by the government and the Department of Education to foster quality education were ineffective. As the country is becoming more advanced in technology, the quality of Philippine education has worsened.

At present, the Philippine educational system is faced by several issues that need to be addressed in order to improve the delivery of education to the most number of the population. One of these is the quality and accessibility of education to its takers. Undeniably, the Philippine government, in spite of its inadequacy of providing some basic services to its people, is doing its best to provide the rudiments of basic schooling to its people for free. Similarly, the 1987 Philippine Constitution provides that public education must be free. This legal mandate resulted to the increase in enrolment of public

elementary and secondary schools. Hence, access to public education is now a right of every Filipino child and a responsibility of the parents.

It is in line with the above that the researcher embarked on the study to assess the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners in Bacsay Elementary School, Camiling West District, Tarlac Province as basis for proposed resource materials during the school year 2022-2023.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Kohlberg's Theory of Moral Development as cited by McLeod (2024) which rests on the principles that unless a reasonable degree of moral development takes place during childhood and adolescence, that is, unless standards of right and wrong are established, the child, and later the adult, is likely to engage in a social behavior, and/or aggressive behavior. On the other hand, if the acceptance of others' standards or the internalization of standards and prohibitions is unduly strong, guilt may develop in association with a wide variety of actions and thoughts. Ideally, individuals workout an adequate serve of morality and at the same time avoid self-condemnation in the context of the culture in which they live.

Lawrence Kohlberg was a developmental theorist of the mid-twentieth century who is best known for his specific and detailed theory of children's moral development. His work continues to be influential today and contemporary research has generally supported his theory.

Kohlberg developed a six stage theory of moral development, and he grouped these six stages into three, higher-order levels of development: 1) the Pre-Conventional Level, 2) the Conventional Level, and 3) the Post-Conventional or Principled Level. Each level is then further sub-divided into two stages to make a total of six stages. The Pre-Conventional Level includes: a) stage one, the punishment and obedience orientation, and b) stage two, the instrumental purpose orientation. The Conventional Level includes: a) stage three, the morality of interpersonal cooperation, and b) stage four, the social-order-maintaining orientation. The Post-Conventional Level includes a) stage five, the social-contract orientation, and b) stage six, the universal ethical principle orientation. This article focuses on the particular stages of moral development associated with adolescent development. Therefore, the discussion begins with stage three, the morality of interpersonal cooperation, within the Conventional Level of moral reasoning.

According to Kohlberg's theory, moral development proceeds in a linear, step-wise fashion; i.e., moral development proceeds gradually from one stage to the next, in a predictable, ordered sequence. Although Kohlberg recognized each child progressed through these stages at different rates, and acknowledged that some youth may never reach the highest stages, his theory does not account for regression back to former, previously mastered stages as do some other developmental theorists.

Kohlberg believed that by early adolescence most youth have reached the mid-level of moral reasoning called the Conventional Level. At this level, morality is determined by social norms; i.e., morality is determined by the rules and social conventions that are explicitly or implicitly agreed upon by a group of people. These rules and customs function to serve to the best interests of the group's majority, while simultaneously providing a structure that maintains social order and limits discord among group members.

The Conventional Level is further subdivided into stage three and stage four. Stage three is called the morality of interpersonal cooperation. At stage three, moral decisions are made by anticipating how a moral decision would be judged by other influential group members. Because youth at this stage wish to be considered a good person and judged in a favorable light, their moral decisions will be based on whether or not their decisions would win the approval of those people whose opinions matter to them.

The next stage within the Conventional Level is stage four, and is called the social-order-maintaining orientation. At this stage, morality is determined by what is best for the majority of people. Furthermore, moral decisions reflect an understanding that the majority of people benefit from a social order that fosters harmonious relationships among group members. At this stage, youth understand that laws are intended to serve everyone's best interest, and believe that societies function best when everyone strictly adheres to the law. These youth will begin to compare their daily decisions, and the consequences of those decisions, to the larger society's moral standards.

This study was also anchored on Gagne's Conditions of Learning Theory as cited by Kurt (2022) which is to help the students establish realistic goals and to assist them in the attainment of goals by eliminating the barriers which block their achievements.

Gagne's theory stipulates that there are several different types or levels of learning. The significance of these classifications is that each different type requires different types of instruction. Gagne identifies five major categories of learning: verbal information, intellectual skills, cognitive strategies, motor skills and attitudes. Different internal and external conditions are necessary for each type of learning. For example, for cognitive strategies to be learned, there must be a chance to practice developing new solutions to problems; to learn attitudes, the learner must be exposed to a credible role model or persuasive arguments.

Gagne suggests that learning tasks for intellectual skills can be organized in a hierarchy according to complexity: stimulus recognition, response generation, procedure following, use of terminology, discriminations, concept formation, rule application, and problem solving. The primary significance of the hierarchy is to identify prerequisites that should be completed to facilitate learning at each level. Prerequisites are identified by doing a task analysis of a learning/training task. Learning hierarchies provide a basis for the sequencing of instruction.

In addition, the theory outlines nine instructional events and corresponding cognitive processes: (1) Gaining attention (reception); (2) Informing learners of the objective (expectancy); (3) Stimulating recall of prior learning (retrieval); (4) Presenting the stimulus (selective perception); (5) Providing learning guidance (semantic encoding); (6) Eliciting performance (responding); (7) Providing feedback (reinforcement); (8) Assessing performance (retrieval); and (9) Enhancing retention and transfer (generalization).

These events should satisfy or provide the necessary conditions for learning and serve as the basis for designing instruction and selecting appropriate media. Gagne provides examples of events for each category of learning outcomes. Different instruction is required for different learning outcomes. Events of learning operate on the learner in ways that constitute the conditions of learning. The specific operations that constitute instructional events are different for each different types of learning outcome. Learning hierarchies define what intellectual skills are to be learned and a sequence of instruction.

Gagne suggests that learning tasks for intellectual skills can be organized in a hierarchy according to complexity: stimulus recognition, response generation, procedure following, use of terminology, discriminations, concept formation, rule application, and problem solving. The primary significance of the hierarchy is to identify prerequisites that should be completed to facilitate learning at each level. Prerequisites are identified by doing a task analysis of a learning/training task. Learning hierarchies provide a basis for the sequencing of instruction.

In addition, the theory outlines nine instructional events and corresponding cognitive processes: Gaining attention (reception); Informing learners of the objective (expectancy); Stimulating recall of prior learning (retrieval); Presenting the stimulus (selective perception); Providing learning guidance (semantic encoding); Eliciting performance (responding); Providing feedback (reinforcement); Assessing performance (retrieval); and Enhancing retention and transfer (generalization). These events should satisfy or provide the necessary conditions for learning and serve as the basis for designing instruction and selecting appropriate media.

The first event of instruction is to gain attention of students so they are alert for the reception of stimuli. An instructor can achieve this by introducing a rapid stimulus change either by gesturing or by suddenly changing the tone or volume of their voice. Another way is by visual or auditory stimuli related to the subject matter.

The second event of instruction is to inform the learner of the purpose and expected outcomes of the learning material. This will provide them with an expectancy that will persist during the time learning is taking place. Feedback at the end of the lesson will provide the learner with confirmation of learning.

The third event of instruction asks the instructor to recall skills or knowledge learners have previously learned. The best kind of recall should naturally relate to the

subject matter being learned. The instructional technique for stimulating recall will be different for the different learning outcomes.

The fourth event of instruction is presenting a stimulus that is related to the subject matter. The content of the stimulus should be specific to the learning outcome. If the stimulus is verbal information, printed prose or an audio tape will achieve the learning objective. If the stimulus is an intellectual skills, the instructor can display the object and/or symbols that will require a concept or rule.

The fifth event of instruction, providing learning guidance requires the instructor to make the stimulus as meaningful as possible. There are several ways to achieve this, depending upon the learning outcome expected. An instructor can enhance meaningfulness by using concrete examples of abstract terms and concepts, and elaborating ideas by relating them to others already in memory.

The sixth instructional event eliciting performance asks a learner to demonstrate the newly learned capability. This may be verbal information, intellectual skills, cognitive strategy, attitude, or motor skill.

The seventh instructional event, providing feedback, asks the instructor to reinforce the newly acquired learning. An instructor can accomplish this through informative feedback where the instructor informs the learner of the degree or correctness or incorrectness of the performance. This feedback may be verbal or written.

The eighth instructional event, assessing performance, consists of assessments to verify that learning has occurred. In order to assure that learning is stable, an instructor will require additional instances of the performance.

The ninth instructional event, enhancing retention and transfer, refers to retaining the learned capability over a long period of time and transferring it into new situations outside of the learning environment. Practice ensures retention, especially with verbal information, intellectual skills and motor skills.

Conceptual Framework

The 1987 Philippine Constitution, PD 9155 also known as Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 and the K to 12 Curriculum serve as the legal basis of the present study.

Every Filipino citizen deserves to be educated. Aware of this, the State is tasked to provide equal educational opportunities to every individual. Explicitly, Section 1 of Article XIV of the 1987 Philippine Constitution states that the State shall protect and provide the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels, and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.

In the promotion of the individual's right to education, "the State shall establish, maintain and support a complete, adequate, and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people and society. It shall likewise establish and maintain a system of free public education in the elementary and high school levels. Without limiting the natural rights of parents to rear their children, elementary education is compulsory for all children of school age.

The Department of Education's Vision, Mission and Values (VMV) statements serve as guiding principles in its unwavering thrust to provide quality education that cultivates passion for the country that is anchored on a set of core values.

The Department of Education (DepEd) vision dreams of Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation. As a learner-centered public institution, DepEd continuously improves itself to better serve its stakeholders.

The DepEd mission is to protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education where students learn in a child-friendly, gender-sensitive, safe, and motivating environment; teachers facilitate learning and constantly nurture every learner; administrators and staff, as stewards of the institution, ensure an enabling and supportive environment for effective learning to happen; family, community, and other stakeholders are actively engaged and share responsibility for developing life-long learners.

Figure 1

Figure 1 presents the schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study through the use of the Input-Process-Output Model.

Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework of the Study

Inputs of the study include how the Grade 3 learners perform in Araling Panlipunan based on the teacher-made test results during the school year 2022-2023 and the weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan in terms of the skills based on the analysis of the test results.

Based on the findings, resource materials were proposed to address the identified weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners. These were evaluated by experts as to their acceptability based on content/subject matter, organization/presentation and physical make-up.

Research Questions

This study assessed the level of performance of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan in Bacsay Elementary School, Camiling West District, Tarlac Province during the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners based on the teacher-made test results?
2. What are the weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan?
3. What resource materials can be proposed to address the identified weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners?
4. How acceptable are the proposed resource materials in Araling Panlipunan for the Grade 3 learners based on the evaluation of experts?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study assessed the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of Grade 3 learners in Bacsay Elementary School, Camiling West District, Tarlac Province during the school year 2022-2023 through quantitative-descriptive research design.

The quantitative-descriptive research design was utilized to assess the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners based on the results of teacher-made tests during school year 2022-2023 as well as their weaknesses in Araling Panlipunan. The acceptability of the developed resource materials was likewise determined based on evaluation of experts in terms of content/subject matter, organization/presentation and physical make-up.

Based on the findings, resource materials in the teaching of Araling Panlipunan were developed to address the weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Sources of Data

The sources of data in this study were the Grade 3 Araling Panlipunan teachers in Bacsay Elementary School, who provided the data needed in the study as well as documents and records to support the data gathered to answer the sub-problems raised in the study. The 21 Grade 3 learners served as the subjects of the study.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The main instruments used in determining the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners in Bacsay Elementary School were the results of teacher-made tests during the school year 2022-2023. The weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan were determined based on the analysis of their performance in teacher-made tests during the school year 2022-2023.

A questionnaire was the data gathering tool to assess the acceptability of the developed resource materials based on evaluation of experts. The questionnaire for acceptability was adopted from Espinar (2017).

Tools for Data Analysis

On the acceptability of the developed resource materials, **weighted mean** was employed to answer sub-problem number 4.

The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum fx$ = the sum of the products per column

N = the number of respondents

To interpret the data, the following reference was used:

Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Acceptable (HA)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Acceptable (VA)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Acceptable (MA)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Acceptable (SA)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Acceptable (NA)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Performance in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 Learners

This section presents the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners of Bacsay Elementary School, Camiling West District, Tarlac Province based on the results of teacher-made tests during the school year 2022-2023 to answer sub-problem number 1.

All learners are expected to perform well in school. In Araling Panlipunan, the ratings of the Grade 3 learners during school year 2022-2023 are shown as follows: Outstanding (95-100%); Above Average (90-94%); Average (85-89%); Fair (80-84%); Poor (75-79%); and Did Not Meet Expectations (Below 75%).

In line with this, Table 1 presents the academic performance in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners in Bacsay Elementary School, Camiling West District, Tarlac Province.

TABLE 1
**Level of Performance in Araling Panlipunan
of the Grade 3 Learners**

Performance Rating	<i>f</i>	%
Outstanding (95-100%)	0	0.00
Above Average (90-94%)	4	19.05
Average (85-89%)	5	23.81
Fair (80-84%)	8	38.09
Poor (75-79%)	4	19.05
Did Not Meet Expectations (Below 75%)	0	0.00
TOTAL	21	100%

As presented in Table 1, no one among the Grade 3 learners obtained outstanding level of performance in Araling Panlipunan or ratings of 95 – 100%. This could mean that no one among the Grade 3 learners had exceeded expectations. No one demonstrated exemplary performance on a majority of activities. There were four learners or 19.05% whose ratings were 90-94% described as above average performance. The learners demonstrated high level of understanding of objectives of the Araling Panlipunan subject. There were five learners or 23.81% with 85-89% rating described as average performance which indicates a satisfactory performance and knowledge of the subject

matter. Most of the Grade 3 learners (8 or 38.09%) had ratings of 80-84% described as fair performance. These learners had weak acquisition of skills and concepts in Araling Panlipunan. Four learners or 19.05% had poor performance with 75-79% ratings and indicate little understanding and acquisition of concepts and skills in Araling Panlipunan.

These results imply the need to develop resource materials in Araling Panlipunan for the Grade 3 learners to enhance their level of performance in the subject for these resource materials play an important role in teaching and learning. They can be used to support and supplement the content of a lesson, help the pupils learn new concepts, and provide practice opportunities. They are essential since they help the teacher and learners avoid overemphasis on recitation and rote learning that can easily dominate a lesson. They allow learners to have practical experiences which help them to develop skills and concepts.

Weaknesses of the Grade 3 Learners in Araling Panlipunan

This section presents the weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan in terms of the skills based on the analysis of the test results to answer sub-problem number 2.

Table 2 presents the data.

TABLE 2
Weaknesses of the Grade 3 Learners
In Araling Panlipunan

Skills/Competencies	Percentage of learners who answered incorrectly
Natatalakay ang pamahalaan at ang mga mamamayan nito	71.68
Natutukoy ang mga pagbabagong nangyayari sa lalawigan at sa kinabibilangang rehiyon	70.36
Naipaliliwanag ang impluwensiya ng klima at lokasyon sa pagbuo at paghubog ng pamumuhay sa isang lugar	67.71
Naipaliliwanag ang kahalagahan ng pamahalaan	64.19
Nailalarawan ang kulturang materyal ng unang Pilipino	58.18

Pagpapahalaga sa mga bayani ng lalawigan at rehiyon	56.27
Nasusuri ang mga uri ng likas na yaman	56.02
Maagap at wastong pagtugon sa mga panganib na madalas maranasan ng sariling rehiyon	54.18
Natutukoy ang relatibong lokasyon ng mga lalawigan sa rehiyon	51.80
Natatalakay ang kultura sa kinabibilangang rehiyon	

As gleaned from Table 2, the Grade 3 learners are weak along the following skills or competencies: Natatalakay ang pamahalaan at ang mga mamamayan nito and natutukoy ang mga pagbabagong nagyayari sa lalawigan at sa kinabibilangang rehiyon with 71.68% and 70.36%, respectively of learners who answered incorrectly; ang impluwensiya ng klima at lokasyon ng isang lugar, ang kahalagahan ng pamahalaan and kulturang materyan ng unang Pilipino with 67.71%, 64.19% and 62.41% of learners with incorrect answers; and five competencies which learners answered incorrectly at the range of 51.80% to 58.18%.

These results imply that there is a need to propose resource materials in Araling Pailipino. More practice, exercises and activities are important for the learners to build their confidence and reinforce important materials. Learners are also provided an opportunity to practice knowledge and skills.

Proposed Resource Materials in Araling Panlipunan

As an output of this study, resource materials in Araling Panlipunan were proposed to address the identified weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners in answer to sub-problem number 3. Additional instructional materials are important since they help the teachers and learners avoid overemphasis on recitation and rote learning that can easily dominate a lesson. Resource materials allow learners to have practical experiences which help them to develop skills and concepts.

Acceptability of the Resource Materials in Araling Panlipunan for Grade 3 Learners

This section is concerned with the acceptability of the proposed resource materials in Araling Panlipunan for Grade 3 learners based on the criteria adopted from Espinar (2017). Table 3 presents the data.

TABLE 3
Acceptability of the Proposed Resource Materials
in Araling Panlipunan

CRITERIA	WM	DE
A. Content/Subject Matter		
The terms and content are suitable to the level of Grade 3 learners.	3.67	VA
The exercises/activities are arranged in the order familiar to Grade 3 learners.	3.50	VA
The instructions are clear and easy to follow.	4.17	VA
The concepts are within the Grade 3 learners' level of experience.	3.50	VA
The number of exercises is limited so as not to overload or confuse the learners.	3.83	VA
Average WM	3.73	VA
B. Organization/Presentation		
The illustrations are clear and interesting.	3.67	VA
The lay-out of the materials can elicit learners' attention.	3.50	VA
The materials are simple and possess imaginative quality.	4.00	VA
Average WM	3.72	VA
C. Physical Make-up		
The instructional design of individual tasks is carefully planned.	4.33	VA
The size of the type and print is proper for the age level of Grade 3 learners.	4.00	VA
The lay-out of the pages has combined attractiveness with utility.	3.67	VA
Average WM	4.00	VA
Overall Average WM	3.82	VA
Legend: <i>WM = weighted mean</i>		
Relative Values	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Acceptable (HA)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Acceptable (VA)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Acceptable (MA)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Acceptable (SA)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Acceptable (NA)

The results of the perceptions of the teachers show that in terms of content, the proposed resource materials are “very acceptable” as evidenced by the weighted mean ranging from 3.50 – 4.17 and by the average weighted mean which is 3.73. These have

something to do with the suitability of the terms and content to the level of Grade 3 learners (WM=3.67); the familiarity of the Grade 3 learners on the arrangement of the exercises (WM=3.50); the clarity of 3learners' level of experience (WM=3.50); and limitation of the number of exercises so as not to overload or confuse the learners (WM=3.83). The results imply that the proposed resource materials can cater to the needs of the Grade 3 learners in terms of content/subject matter.

On the quality of the presentation, the average weighted mean is 3.72 which means "very acceptable". This particular criterion includes the picture being clear and interesting (WM=3.67); the layout of the materials can elicit children's attention (WM=3.50); and capability of the materials and their possessions of imaginative quality (WM=4.00). Thus, the results imply that the proposed resource materials meet the criteria for quality of organization/presentation.

As to physical make-up, the average weighted mean is 4.00 for a descriptive equivalent of "very acceptable." This includes careful planning of the instructional design of individual tasks (WM=4.33); proper size of the type and print for the age level of Grade 3 learners (WM=4.00); and combined attractiveness with utility of the layout of the pages (WM=3.67).

Overall, the average weighted mean is 3.82 which means that the proposed resource materials are "very acceptable" as perceived by the English teachers

Based on the results, the developed resource materials are accepted by the teachers. This implies that the materials could be used as a tool in enhancing the Grade 3 learners' performance in Araling Panlipunan.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the Grade 3 learners had fair level of performance in Araling Panlipunan which indicates they have a weak acquisition of concepts and skills in the learning area.
2. Weaknesses in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners include the following: Natatalakay ang pamahalaan at ang mga mamamayan nito; natutukoy ang mga pagbabagong nagyayari sa lalawigan at sa kinabibilangang rehiyon; and naipaliliwanag ang impluwensiya ng klima at lokasyon sa pagbuo at paghubog ng pamumuhay sa isang lugar.
3. The proposed resource materials were developed to address the weaknesses in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade 3 learners and improve their level of performance.
4. The proposed resource materials are very acceptable based on the evaluation of experts.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn as a result of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The developed resource materials should be considered for use by concerned authorities.
 2. Parents and teachers should communicate regularly relative to the learners' performance in school.
 3. The developed resource materials should be tried out on a wider scale for further improvement.
 4. Teachers should be encouraged to develop instructional materials particularly on subjects or topics where most learners encounter difficulties.
 5. The school administration should provide support in the production of materials developed by teachers.
 6. Other researchers may conduct similar studies on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in Bacsay Elementary School, Camiling West District, Tarlac Province during the school year 2022-2023. It focused on the assessment of the performance of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan.

The specific concerns of the study are the following: (1) level of performance in Araling Panlipunan based on teacher-made test results; and (2) weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners in Araling Panlipunan based on the analysis of the test results. Based on the findings, resource materials were proposed to address the identified weaknesses of the Grade 3 learners.

Acknowledgments

In embarking on this academic journey, the author finds it essential to extend her heartfelt appreciation to those who have been instrumental in the completion of this study.

The author of this book is very grateful to GOD ALMIGHTY for without his graces and blessings, this study would not have been possible.

Also, immeasurable pleasure and deepest gratitude for the help and support are extended to the following persons who in one way or another have been contributed in making this study possible.

To Dr. Ricky C. Junio, her thesis adviser, for his unwavering support, advice, guidance, valuable comments, suggestions, and provisions that benefited her much in the completion and success of this study.

To her respondents and co - teachers, for their worthy support and cooperation and time in terms of providing the author all the needed information.

To Edna A. Collado (deceased), her aunt, whose love, care and encouragement have been the source of her strength to pursue this study.

To Carlito V. Vallente and Marlyn C. Vallente, her parents, for their endless support and love as well as their unfailing guidance that made this far and be able to achieve her dreams and ambition in life.

To Jun Raymund V. Carlos, her husband, who stood by through all travails, fits of pique and impatience, for the unwavering and unconditional support, love and encouragement to complete this academic journey.

In the end, this study stands as a testament to the collective efforts and support of those mentioned above. Thank you for being an integral part of this academic milestone.

REFERENCES

- Baliling, V. (2020). "Multiple Intelligences Strategies in Teaching Araling Panlipunan among Public Secondary Schools in the City Division of Tabuk, Kalinga." *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*.
- Crisolo, O. (2017). "Relevance of Social Studies in the 21st Century Society: Students' Perspectives." Ramon Magsaysay Technological University.
- Espinar, M. (2017). "Content Validity and Acceptability of a Developed Worktext." *International Conference on Research in Social Sciences, Humanities and Education*.
- Guimba, W., Aquino, J. & Abbas, B. (2016). "Attitudes Related to Social Studies among Grade 9 Students at MSU – ILS." *International Conference on Research in Social Sciences, Humanities and Education*.
- Inocian, R. (2014). "Social Studies Teachers' Proclivities to Teach World History in the New K to 12 Curriculum in the Philippines." Cebu Normal University.
- Kurt, S. (2022). "Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction." *Education Library*.
- Macarandan, R. (2014). "Assessment of the Araling Panlipunan Modules in the K-12 Curriculum: Enhanced Industrial Materials Development."
- Kohlberg, L. (1969). "Jean Piaget's Theory of Moral Judgement for Children (1932)"
- McLeod, S. (2024). "Kohlberg's Stages of Moral Development." *Simply Psychology*.
- Pangilinan, J. (2021). "Emergence of 21st Century Instructional Strategies in Araling Panlipunan Instruction: A Comparative Study among Selected Secondary Schools in Eastern Samar, Philippines." *Asian Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences*.
-